

How I Came to Believe in My Theories

Miloš Večeřa

Everything on Zenodo originated from a great emotional storm unlike anything I had ever experienced in my life. That intensity was the source and essence of my discovery. Moments of genius among people who could observe my work gave me confidence that I was not alone. The madness that began to surround me and the questions that encircled my mind can be found in a document on Zenodo.

The greatest anxiety of my life came a few days ago, when two people I mentioned helped me. When I wrote a critique of false Popperism, I realized that my crystals are real — they cannot be falsified, just like a crystal of pure gold. Yes, I had death on my tongue — my heart was pounding and I felt enormous pressure in my kidneys (adrenal glands). I surely would not die because of nonsense.

After completing the work, the greatest balance in my life came — I laugh and cry at the same time, and that is COOL. Yesterday I was at the hairdresser's, I just had to say "I have everything," and maybe she would have started seducing me — again, COOL. Perhaps there is a hidden new kind of language in this.

I believe that this can be used not only in education but also in healthcare — a balanced state can eliminate stress and help colleagues achieve guided discoveries (intuition). Now I feel only present (no more intuitions), and I have only the need for desire.

Within a few days, I lost several kilograms and only after 14 days did I feel true hunger. My kidneys still hurt, but I believe I will soon be healthy. :)

Proof of the Theory

The proof of this theory is my own experience. Therefore, this theory is lived, and that is its proof.